

**IDENTIFICATION OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE RESTORATION
OF TRAIN TRAFFIC AFTER MOVEMENT BREAKS IN RAILWAY
SECTIONS**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to analyze the factors affecting the resumption of train traffic and this recovery after breaks in train movement for unexpected technical and technological reasons in railway sections According to the result of these analyzes, it was taken as a basis to increase the capacity for conducting in the reconstruction of the movement of trains on one-way and two-way sections.

Keywords: section, break, restoration, analysis, technical and technological reason, train movement, transfer capacity.

Introduction

Great importance are the issues of organizing the movement of trains during and after the movement break on any railway site [1-9, 12-14]. Usually breaks are divided into two groups [1, 7, 10-12]: planned and unplanned (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Classification of train movement breaks

In order to effectively organize the transportation process, the main task of organizing the movement of trains during scheduled breaks is to skip scheduled wagon flows and passenger trains along railway sections and routes on schedule in a timely manner [10-18]. The main criterion in this is to reduce the delay train hours during the train break and ineffective time losses in the work of stations [12-19].

An unplanned break is a violation of the safety of movement of trains due to various random factors during the voluntary time of the day [6-9, 12-18]. The main criterion in this type of break is to minimize the recovery time of train movement when choosing the most convenient option for organizing train movement (option with a minimum of train-hours or wagon-hours) after the elimination of the malfunction that occurred [1, 3, 5-9].

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The recovery time of train traffic on railway sections and routes depends on the following main factors [1, 7, 12, 18]: number of main roads; type of traction (diesel locomotive or electric locomotive); type of communication on the sections (automatic

blocking system, electric jezl system,...); amount of movement of freight and passenger trains on the section.

Based on the analysis of the scientific work [1-19] carried out to restore the movement of trains after movement breaks in railway sections, factors affecting the movement of trains were determined. Factors sections were described in the form of the Isikavi scheme according to the technical classification, the amount of movement, the time of the break in movement and the criteria for the methods of organizing movement (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Factors affecting the recovery time of train movement (t_{rec})

Based on Figure 2, some factors were analyzed that significantly affect the restoration of train traffic. In particular, in order to reduce the recovery time of movement in one-way sections by (t_{rec}), it is required to identify and evaluate the influence of the following factors: duration of the break t_{break} ; number of head roads on the section; trains amount of movement– N ; number of roads at the station– G .

The number of trains delayed at the time of the break for one-way sections when an unplanned break or a planned “free period” appears is determined as follows

$$N_{\text{delay}} = \frac{N}{24} \cdot t_{\text{break, train}} \quad (1)$$

On one-way sections, during the recovery time of the movement, it is required to first skip trains delayed during the break, and then, after that, trains that have just arrived at the site. In this case

$$N_{\text{delay}} = \frac{N}{1440} \cdot t_{\text{break}} = \frac{t_{\text{rec}}}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}} - \frac{t_{\text{rec}}}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{norm}}}, \text{ train} \quad (2)$$

there $T_{\text{period}}^{\text{norm}}$ – normative graph period, minutes;

$T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}$ – graphic period in the recovery time of the action after the break, minute.

This value depends on the schemes for transferring trains along a one-way sections. In the general case, the graph period is determined by the following expression

$$T_{\text{period}} = t' + \tau_{\text{int.sec}} + t'' + \tau_{\text{one.arrival}}, \text{ minute} \quad (3)$$

there $\tau_{\text{int.sec}}$ – intersection interval of trains at separation points, minutes;

$\tau_{\text{one.arrival}}$ – interval of non-simultaneous arrival of trains to separation points, minutes;

t', t'' – times of trains running along passage in odd and even directions, respectively, minutes.

(2)-based on the expression, the recovery time of the action (t_{rec}) is determined as follows:

$$t_{\text{rec}} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}} - \frac{1}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{norm}}} \right) = t_{\text{break}} \cdot \frac{N}{1440}, \text{ minute}$$

$$t_{\text{rec}} = \frac{N}{\left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}} - \frac{1}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{norm}}} \right)} \cdot t_{\text{break}} = \frac{N \cdot T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}}{1440 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{norm}}} \right)} \cdot t_{\text{break}}, \text{ minute} \quad (4)$$

In this case, the recovery time of movement on a one-way sections in (i-break) is determined by the following formula:

$$t_{\text{rec}}^i = \frac{N \cdot t_{\text{break}}}{1440 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}} - \frac{1}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{norm}}} \right)}, \text{ minute} \quad (5)$$

The transfer volume coefficient is determined by the following formula:

$$k = \frac{N}{N_{\max} \frac{(1440-t'_{\text{break}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{pack}} \cdot T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}} \cdot T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{norm}} \cdot (1440-t'_{\text{break}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{pack}} \cdot T_{\text{period}}^{\text{norm}}}} \quad (6)$$

there $N_{\max}$ maximum trains amount of movement;

α_{pack} – packing factor.

(6)-based on the expression, the recovery time of the action (t_{rec}) can be determined by the following formula:

$$t_{\text{rec}} = t_{\text{break}} \cdot \frac{N \cdot T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}}{1440 \cdot (1-k)}, \text{ minute} \quad (7)$$

(5)-and (6)-the following can be obtained using expressions

$$N = N_{\max} \frac{(1440-t'_{\text{break}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{pack}}}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}} \quad (8)$$

(7)-and (8)-the recovery time of an action at a break in a one-way section in a single-way graph type based on expressions can be determined by the following formula:

$$t_{\text{rec}} = t_{\text{break}} \cdot \frac{\frac{(1440-t'_{\text{break}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{pack}}}{T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}} \cdot k \cdot T_{\text{period}}^{\text{rec}}}{1440 \cdot (1-k)} = t_{\text{break}} \cdot \frac{(1440-t'_{\text{break}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{pack}} \cdot k}{1440 \cdot (1-k)}, \text{ minute} \quad (9)$$

$$t_{\text{rec}}^i = t_{\text{break}} \cdot \frac{(1440-t'_{\text{break}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{pack}} \cdot k}{1440 \cdot (1-k)}, \text{ minute} \quad (10)$$

Factors affecting the recovery time of movement on one-way sections.

- The following factors influence the recovery time of movement on two-way sections (at the time of the planned break):

- number of trains in the movement caught during the break;
- number of trains entering the sections after the end of the break.

In addition, the following factors can influence the recovery time of the action on the timeout on two-way sections:

- Up to 4 hours – the recovery time of movement is not influenced by factors;
- From 4 to 8 hours – the number of reception-transferring routes at stations delimiting the repaired passage;
- From 8 to 12 hours – the amount of movement of trains and the development of road networks of stations delimiting the repaired passage;

- From 12 to 14 hours – the development of road networks of stations delimiting the repaired passage;

- From 14 to 20 hours – the amount of movement of trains, the distance of the repaired site from the sorting station, the development of road networks of stations delimiting the repaired passage;

- From 20 to 24 hours – all of the above factors have a huge impact on the recovery time of the usual train movement.

In order to reduce (minimize) (t_{rec}) the recovery time of the action on the plot, it is required to identify and evaluate the influence of the following factors:

- duration of the break – t_{break} ;
- number of head roads on the section;
- transfer volume replenishment coefficient – k ;
- number of roads at the station – G ;
- the length of the passage, which is used as a temporary one-way – $l_{passage}$.

Let's take a look at the impact of the above factors on t_{rec} during a planned break
If number of trains caught

$$N_{tr.caught} = \frac{N}{1440} \cdot t_{break} - \frac{t_{break}}{T_{free.period}} = \frac{t_{rec}}{I_{rec}} - \frac{t_{rec}}{I_{norm}}, \text{ train} \quad (11)$$

In this case:
$$\frac{t_{rec}}{I_{rec}} - \frac{t_{rec}}{I_{norm}} = \frac{N}{1440} \cdot t_{break} - \frac{t_{break}}{T_{free.period}}$$

$$t_{rec} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{I_{rec}} - \frac{1}{I_{norm}} \right) = t_{break} \cdot \left(\frac{N}{1440} - \frac{1}{T_{free.period}} \right),$$

$$t_{rec} = t_{break} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{N}{1440} - \frac{1}{T_{free.period}} \right)}{\left(\frac{1}{I_{rec}} - \frac{1}{I_{norm}} \right)} = t_{break} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{N}{1440} - \frac{1}{T_{free.period}} \right)}{\frac{1}{I_{rec}} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{I_{rec}}{I_{norm}} \right)} = t_{break} \cdot$$

$$\frac{\left(\frac{N}{1440} - \frac{1}{T_{free.period}} \right) \cdot I_{rec}}{1 - \frac{I_{rec}}{I_{norm}}}, \text{ minute} \quad (12)$$

The transfer volume coefficient can be determined by the following expression:

$$k = \frac{N}{N_{\max} \frac{(1440-t'_{\text{break}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{pack}} \cdot I_{\text{rec}}}{I_{\text{norm}} \cdot (1440-t'_{\text{break}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{rec}} \cdot I_{\text{norm}}}} \quad (13)$$

In this case:

$$t'_{\text{rec}} = t_{\text{break}} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{N}{1440} \frac{1}{T_{\text{free.period}}} \right) \cdot I_{\text{rec}}}{1-k}, \text{ minute} \quad (14)$$

(11)÷(14)-the recovery time of movement in a two-way sections in (i-break), derived from the expressions, is determined by the following expression:

$$t'_{\text{rec}} = t_{\text{break}} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{(1440-t'_{\text{break}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{pack}}}{1440 \cdot I_{\text{rec}}} \cdot k - \frac{1}{T_{\text{free.period}}} \right) \cdot I_{\text{rec}}}{1-k}, \text{ minute} \quad (15)$$

CONCLUSION

Railway traffic is listed according to the types of stops that occur in the train schedule. Also, methods of normalization of inefficient time indicators lost in the process of resuming train movement after interruptions caused by planned and unexpected reasons were discussed. As a result of this study, the factors that have a direct impact on increasing the ability to transfer after breaks were analyzed.

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